

Wide adaptability of new rice cultivars developed by the Japan-China collaborative project in Yunnan, China

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China's Yunnan Province is considered to be one of the centers of genetic diversity in Asian cultivated rice. A collaborative research project between JIRCAS and YAAS for lowland japonica rice breeding using a wide diversity of genetic resources has been conducted in Yunnan since 1982. New rice cultivars developed through the joint project have been grown widely in and around the province since 1989. In 1997, the total area of these cultivars covered more than 200,000 ha, accounting for more than 40% of the japonica rice-growing area and about 20% of the total rice-growing area in Yunnan.

In 1996, two rice cultivars, Hexi 34 and Hexi 35, were developed and released by the project; they were officially registered in 1997 by the Yunnan provincial government. Hexi 34 was developed from the cross Yunxi 2/ Dianyu 1, and Hexi 35 from the cross Hexi 15/Hexi 4. The pedigree of these new cultivars can be traced to some Japanese rice genetic resources: high-yielding cultivar Todorokiwase, blast-resistant germplasm accessions BL 1 and BL 6, and others. Todorokiwase, especially, was the most useful Japanese cultivar, with resistance to cool weather and blast resistance for improving the grain quality and high yielding ability of Yunnan rice in the breeding program.

Agronomic performance of Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 in regional trials in Yunnan, China.

Character	Hexi 34	Hexi 35	Yunkeng 9 (standard)
Growth duration (d)	187	178	185
Culm length (cm)	92	93	111
Panicle length (cm)	19.0	17.8	16.4
Panicles (no. m ⁻²)	417	388	387
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	109	118	131
Panicle fertility (%)	79.3	81.4	71.5
Single-grain weight (mg)	26.3	25.8	22.7
Yielding ability (%)	123	126	100
Lodging resistance	HR ^a	HR	S
Cool-weather resistance	MR	MR	MR
Blast resistance	HR	M	R
Grain appearance	Good	Good	Poor
Eating quality	Good	Good	Poor

^aHR = high resistance, MR = moderate resistance, M = moderate, S = susceptible.

The principal reason for releasing these two cultivars is that they have a higher yielding ability than current japonica rice cultivars grown in Yunnan, which is the most important factor in crop production in China. Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 performed very well in the uniform trials conducted at 12 sites representative of japonica rice-growing areas in the central and northern parts of Yunnan (see table). In 24 tests across 12 locations during a 2-yr period, the average yields of Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 were 8.4 and 8.6 t ha⁻¹, respectively, compared with 6.9 t ha⁻¹ for the standard cultivar Yunkeng 9.

We conducted a statistical analysis of adaptation based on the data of the uniform trials using the linear regression method. The regression coefficients on the mean yield of each environment for Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 were smaller than those for other cultivars tested (see figure). The findings indicate that these cultivars with high yield potential are well adapted to different environments in Yunnan.

The cooking and processing qualities of Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 are superior to those of standard cultivar Yunkeng 9 in Yunnan. Milled kernels of Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 are nonglutinous and non-aromatic; they are translucent in contrast to those of Yunkeng 9, which show a pronounced white belly. Taste panelists rated Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 as

satisfactory in sensory tests of steamed rice. The rapidly rising living standard in urban areas of China has resulted in a remarkable increase in demand for rice with a good taste. These two new cultivars will meet the demand for good-quality rice and could be widely grown in and around Yunnan Province because of their high yielding ability and high grain quality.

Finally, we should pay careful attention to the shift in the frequency of blast fungus races. Hexi 34 and Hexi 35 exhibit a race-specific resistance to rice blast disease, the most devastating disease in Yunnan's japonica rice-growing areas.

Cultivar performance by regression coefficient and mean yield in 24 environments in Yunnan, China.

But the breakdown of blast resistance is common in many rice-growing areas, often shortly after the release of culti-

vars with race-specific resistance. We should therefore develop breeding strategies for durable resistance to

reduce the impact of rice blast disease by using the abundant rice genetic resources of Yunnan and Japan. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

Karnataka rice hybrids

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For more than a decade, farmers in the irrigated area of Karnataka harvested yields of up to 7 t ha⁻¹. No new technologies could help them increase yield further. Therefore, the major objective of the hybrid rice research begun at Mandya was to identify a suitable hybrid that could yield at least 1 t more than the check varieties. This objective was fulfilled by the release in 1994 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and in 1996 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 (KRH2). The hybrid KRH1 (IR58025A/IR9761-19-1R) has a yield potential of 7.5-8.5 t ha⁻¹ and matures in 125 d. In 150 on-farm irrigated trials conducted in farmers' fields in different districts, KRH1 had a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over the check varieties. This hybrid possesses field tolerance for major pests and diseases.

Medium-duration hybrid KRH2 (IR58025A and KMR3) matures in 135 d and yields at least 1.0 t ha⁻¹ more than the best check variety, Jaya. In addition, it has a better straw yield and exhibits tolerance for blast. Therefore, farmers are impressed by its performance. This hybrid is semitall with long, slender grains. In 15 other trials conducted at Mandya from 1992 to 1995, KRH2 produced an average of 9.3 t ha⁻¹ with a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya. Similarly, multilocation, multiseasonal experiments conducted at different research stations in Karnataka in irrigated areas also confirmed the superiority of KRH2, with at least 1.2 t ha⁻¹ more yield than Jaya. This hybrid was found to be more stable over locations. KRH2 recorded the highest yields in national trials during 1995, with a yield

advantage of more than 0.9 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya.

Agronomic experiments with these hybrids indicated that the recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for semidwarf varieties is also suitable for these hybrids. Planting one seedling hill⁻¹ and 20- × 10-cm spacing are recommended for this hybrid. A seed rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ is sufficient. ■

TNRH16: a salt-tolerant rice hybrid

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Among abiotic stresses, salinity-alkalinity is the major constraint to yield in rice. Experience in other crops indicates that hybrids perform better than varieties under adverse growing conditions. A study was therefore made to evaluate hybrids involving salt-tolerant parental lines. Ten male sterile lines with their respective B lines and 24 restorer lines were screened under natural salt-stress conditions (pH 9.0

and EC 0.21 dS m⁻¹). Of these, IR62829A, IR66707A, and IR58025A were more tolerant. A similar response was recorded in their respective B lines. Of the 24 restorer lines, only six had good phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth. Assuming that the additive complementary effect of tolerant A and R lines in the hybrid would enhance the level of salt tolerance, hybrids involving such parental lines were evaluated for salt tolerance. All F₁ hybrids derived using IR62829A and IR58025A as male sterile lines, though poor yielders, proved quite tolerant, with high phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth from seedling to flowering. A high pollen or spikelet number during the last phase possibly resulted in poor grain yields. TNRH16, derived from moderately salt-tolerant parents (IR58025A/C20R), was the only exception. This hybrid recorded a grain yield of 5,002 kg ha⁻¹, whereas the salt-tolerant check, Co 43, recorded 4,160 kg ha⁻¹. The standard heterosis was 23%. The higher grain yield of TNRH16 may also be attributed to the fact that parental characters for sodicity tolerance get complemented in the F₁ hybrid. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Differentiation of rice tungro spherical virus variants by RT-PCR and RFLP

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Rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) is one of the two causal agents of rice tungro disease, the most important viral disease of rice in South and Southeast Asia. RTSV assists in the semipersistent transmission of rice

tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), the other causal agent, which causes the symptoms.

RTSV is a single-stranded RNA virus of 12,180 nucleotides (Hull 1996). Genome organization shows that it encodes a large polyprotein of 393 kDa, which contains the three coat proteins (CP1, CP2, and CP3), motifs for nucleotide triphosphate (NTP) binding domain, protease (PRO), and polymerase (POL). The polyprotein is thought to be cleaved by the virus-